

Influence of Choosing and Selection Works On the Milk Productivity of Cows

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Abstract

The article presents information about the influence of choosing and selection works on the milk productivity of black and white breed cows of milk direction.

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Introduction. Building large complexes in specializing animal husbandry and changing it to the basis of industry requires creating herds adapted to industrial technology. In this, it is necessary to choose animals according to their adaptability to new technological conditions and technological indicators.

The main technological indicators are live weight, consistency of constitution, adapting to machine milking, productivity endurance to diseases, leg consistency, fertility, behavior of animals.

Similar and high productive herds and herds of the same type are necessary for milk producing complexes. Average weight of healthy cows should be 500-600 kg and milk productivity - 4000-5000 kg. It is necessary in feeding them in similar type and degree.

The actuality of the theme. Farms direct developing herds by keeping animals which have expedient peculiarities, and removing animals, which have unfavorable indicators from the herd. In this, the higher requirement for selection and assessing cattle according to economic indicators, the higher will be productivity of breed.

Farm animals, especially, cattle are selected one by one according to their complex indicators and origin, exterior and constitution, live weight, milk and meat productivity, milk fatness, milk giving velocity, milky coefficient, protein amount of milk, udder structure, industrial ability of chosen calves of milking cows.

Results of the selection are dependent on the breeding of animals. Transmissions from generation to generation determines breeding quality of animals, and surrounding environment serves to appearance and consistency of them. So, genotype and phenotype of animals are directly connected with each other and they are formed by qualitative feeding and keeping cattle on the basis of zoohygienic requirements. Therefore, choosing and selection by aim are one of the resulting methods of selection works.

The object of the research. Cattle in the milk direction, black and white breed, daily milk productivity, average milk productivity, milk fatness.

The method of the research. Zootechnical and biological methods.

Scientific-research works. Productivity indicators of cattle, influence of breeding works on milk productivity of black and white breed cows in the milk direction were studied in the farm conditions "Kiyat-Akhunkaragan" in Shumanay region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Received results. It is important to choose cows according to the udder scale, form, nipples, equal development of parts, udder index, milk giving velocity, milking time and other indicators in order to change into milking by machine.

The most important morphological sign of udder is its form. Udders are divided into like a bath, like a bowl, round and goat udder types according to their form.

Udder like a bath differs from others with its large scale, good development of front and back sides, smooth scale, equal development of parts, wide location of nipples from each other.

Udder like a bowl differs from others with its large scale and consistent uniteness with abdomen. In this type of udder, front and back sides are slightly equal developed, nipples are located widely and straight directed.

Round udder is smaller; its parts are underneath well developed. The part, which is united to the body, is smaller.

Goat udder is differed with its bad uniteness to the body, bad development of front parts, complex and dense location of nipples.

Cows with udders like a bath and bowl are well adapted to milking by machine but cows with goat udder are unfit for milking by machine.

There is a connection between udder form and milk productivity of cows.

Table 1

Connection between udder form and milk productivity of cows

Breeds	Udder forms					
	Like a bowl		Round		Goat udder	
	n	During the lactation, kg	n	During the lactation, kg	n	During the lactation, kg
Black and white	5	2980	5	2786	5	2252
Red-desert	5	2750	5	2380	5	1900

Milk productivity of cows with udder like a bowl is higher by 10-20% from the cows with round udder, and multiplication of milk productivity of cows with goat udder brings into the improvement of udder form. But in order to fastening improvement of udder form of cows it is necessary to carry out durable selection works on udder form. Cows with goat udder should be slowly replaced with first born cows. If it is done like this, udder form of cows in herds will be improved.

Copulating and selection of agricultural animals are the main methods of zootechnics.

Selection actively serves for carrying out copulating, so copulating do not give good results without selection. Copulating strengthens the result of selection and reaches to its aim.

The basic principles of copulating: its expedient direction, being superior of pedigree male animals from female animals, preventing relativeness between copulating animals and controlling its degree should be taken into consideration, copulating should be carried out in a similar form, if the number of animals in the farm does not correspond to the aim, the result of copulating will not be good.

Copulating is divided into similar or homogeneous and different heterogeneous copulating according to the similarities of copulating female and male animals. Similarities of animals can be according to some indicators. For example, in milk cattle breeding milk productivity of cows can be improved and strengthened by homogeneous copulating.

In heterogeneous copulating heterozygous or changeability increases, living abilities improved, constitution strengthened. Heterogeneous copulating can correct deficiency of animals with the help of other animals.

Homogeneous or heterogeneous copulating is carried out on the following indicators:

1. According to constitution. Copulating constitutional similar animals is homogeneous copulating. In this, male animal with consistent constitution is copulated with female animal with consistent constitution. If an animal with consistent constitution is copulated, it will be heterogeneous copulating.

2. According to productivity. If milk giving cow is copulated with male animal, which is appropriate to much milky line, it will be homogeneous copulating. If milky cow with a little fatness is copulated with a bull, which has much fatness and in a milky line, it will be heterogeneous copulating.

3. Copulating according to origin and living conditions. If animals in the same condition and on one farm are copulated, it will be homogeneous copulating.

4. Copulating according to the line. If male and female animals of one line are copulated, it is homogeneous, if correctly choosing and copulating-selection of male and female animals of different lines are carried out on the basis of methodical way, parents are chosen correctly, homogenates are selected, breeding qualities, productivity peculiarities of their generation will be improved. This can be seen in pedigree farms. The results of choosing and selection works carried out in pedigree farms are given in the following table 2.

Table 2

Indicators of results of choosing and selection works carried out in pedigree farms

Nº	Breed of cattle	Number of cows, n	Live weight, kg	milked amount in 305 days (kg)	Fatness in milk, %	Expenses of fatness in milk, kg	Milky coefficiency, kg
1	Black and white	50	610	5320	4,1	218	855
2	Black and white	50	520	4180	3,8	161	750

As can be seen from the information of the table, when choosing and selection works were conducted correctly in breeding, amount of milk received from cows, fatness percent in milk and fatness expenses, milky coefficient were higher, when choosing and selection were carried out on average level, they were lower. This shows the effectiveness of choosing and selection.

Conclusion. Improving breeding works, correctly choosing and selecting pedigree cattle are conducted on a farm. It brings into the improvement of breeding qualities of milking cows, increasing milk productivity year by year.

All of the above mentioned actions are directed to improve the breed of agricultural animals and increase their productivity in order to fully satisfy with the requirement of people for food and industry for raw material.

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